

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 67 (2026) 1-15

EISSN 2543-5426

Documenting Plants Used for Treating Infantile Eela in Abeokuta South, Ogun State, Nigeria: An Ethno-pharmacological Survey

S. O. Mujeeb¹, O. D. Umoren^{1,2,*} and O. O. Osifeso³

¹ Department of Biological Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria

² Biological Science Research Unit, Pure Sciences, Abeokuta, Ogun state, Nigeria

³ Environmental Science and Management Technology, Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Ogun State, Nigeria

*E-mail address: otohifedayo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Traditional medicine plays an important role in the management of infantile skin disorders in many developing countries. This study investigates the use of medicinal plants for the treatment of infantile seborrheic dermatitis (ISDs) in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Sixty (60) structured questionnaires were administered to herb sellers, nursing mothers, and traditional medical practitioners. The results revealed that majority of respondents were females (85%), between 18–40 years (45%), followed by those above 60 years (30%). Knowledge of infantile seborrheic dermatitis was universal among respondents (100%), and 95% reported awareness of herbal remedies used for its treatment. Indigenous knowledge of herbal medicine was largely inherited from parents (85%). A total of fifteen medicinal plants were identified for the management of ISDs. Trees constituted the dominant habit form (73%), while leaves were the most frequently used plant parts (50%). The most common preparation methods were cooking (47%) and decoction (35%), while water (86%) was the primary solvent used. Bathing was the predominant mode of application (72%). The findings highlight the importance of traditional medicinal plants in infant health care and emphasize the need for further phytochemical and pharmacological validation of these plants.

Keywords: Ethno-pharmacology, Medicinal Plants, Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis, Abeokuta South

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants continue to attract global scientific attention due to their rich diversity of bioactive compounds and their relevance in modern and traditional healthcare systems. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that over 80% of the world's population relies on plant-based remedies as their primary source of healthcare, especially in developing countries where accessibility to conventional drugs is limited (Umoren *et al.*, 2022; Ansari *et al.*, 2025). These plants contain numerous phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, glycosides, and saponins that exert a wide range of pharmacological effects including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anticancer, and antioxidant activities (Sarsodia and Dubey, 2025; Osifeso *et al.*, 2025).

Medicinal plants are vital not only as traditional therapeutic agents but also as sources for drug discovery and development (Hashim *et al.*, 2025). Recent systematic reviews highlight the broad therapeutic range of medicinal plants across major disease categories (Mouminah, 2024; Sarsodia and Dubey, 2025; Ansari *et al.*, 2025). Although, despite the promising therapeutic potential of medicinal plants, challenges remain regarding standardization, dosage, and clinical validation. Many studies are limited to *in vitro* or animal models, with few progressing to clinical trials (Ansari *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, variability in plant growth conditions, extraction methods, and phytochemical composition complicates reproducibility and quality control (Umoren *et al.*, 2021; Oguntibeju, 2025).

Researchers has documented that plant can be used for the treatment of numerous diseases and ailments. In a study by Adeniyi *et al.* (2018) medicinal plant can be used to cure malaria, respiratory tract infections, diabetics, stomach ache, cancer, toothache, sexual impotence, gonorrhoea, malaria, dysmenorrhoea and abdominal pain. Another study by Mangali *et al.* (2021) reported that plants are used for the treatments of diseases such as urinary tract infection, cough and flu, burns and wounds. Furthermore, Umoren *et al.* (2022) has reported that plants are used for treating diseases in children.

Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis (ISD) is a common, non-contagious inflammatory skin condition that affects infants within the first few months of life, typically resolving between 6 and 12 months (Laughter *et al.*, 2021; Onipede *et al.*, 2025). Although not life-threatening, ISD can cause parental anxiety, discomfort in infants, and significant aesthetic and hygienic concerns (Al-Hammadi *et al.*, 2022). Conventional treatments often rely on topical antifungal agents, mild corticosteroids, and emollients; however, the use of these agents can be limited by side effects, cost, accessibility, and cultural preferences (Smith and Tan, 2023). Consequently, herbal remedies remain a widely accepted and accessible alternative in many developing regions, including Nigeria (Odeyemi and Amoo, 2020).

Abeokuta, the capital of Ogun State in southwestern Nigeria, represents a unique ethnobotanical landscape due to its rich cultural heritage and deep-rooted traditional healing practices (Orunto Owu, 2025). The Yoruba people of this region possess extensive indigenous knowledge of medicinal plants used to manage a variety of ailments, including dermatological disorders (Aboh *et al.*, 2023).

Despite this, there is a paucity of documented evidence on specific herbal formulations employed in the treatment or maintenance of infantile skin disorders such as seborrheic dermatitis. The ethnobotanical documentation in of this plants is essential to preserve traditional medical knowledge, validate its therapeutic claims, and guide pharmacological exploration (Nnadi *et al.*, 2021).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The study was conducted in the Abeokuta, Ogun State, South-Western Nigeria. Abeokuta is the capital and largest urban centre of Ogun State in southwestern Nigeria, serving as an important cultural, economic and historical hub in the Yoruba region. Located on the east bank of the Ogun River amidst granite outcrops and wooded savanna-terrain, the settlement is approximately 80 km north of Lagos. Abeokuta has historically been an agricultural trade centre: key crops include rice, yams, cassava, maize, palm kernels, fruits and cotton. The area also hosts traditional textile production especially *adire* (tie-dye cloth) and has small-scale industries such as sawmills, plastics, and fruit-canning (Orunto Owu, 2025). As the capital of Ogun State which itself was created by carving out parts of the old Western Region in 1976 (Ogun State Government, 2025).

2. 2. Study Design

The study adopted a stratified research design; by this method the researcher used structured questionnaires to obtain data from a selected sample of the population in order to make a generalization for the purpose of the study.

2. 3. Data Collection

Source of data collection are primary source which include a set of questionnaires. The source of data requires the administration of a questions to respondent in order to support the finding of the research.

2. 4. Questionnaire Administration

A total sixty (60) questionnaires were randomly administered to respondents (herb sellers, nursing mothers, traditional medical practitioners) to obtain information about the medicinal plants use for maintaining infantile seborrheic dermatitis in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. **Section A:** demography such as gender, age group, profession, religion and level of education. **Section B:** knowledge of medicinal plants such as the source of medicinal plant usage knowledge, years of experience, **Section C:** list of medicinal plants used in treatment of different ailments., which is divide into name of plant, habit of plant, parts used, mode of preparation of plant material, solvent (additives) used and method of use.

2. 5. Data Analysis

Data was analyzed in frequency and percentage tables while Microsoft excel 2016 is use to generate graphical representation.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1. The results show that females constituted the majority of respondents (85%), while males accounted for

15%. The age distribution revealed that 45% of the respondents were between 18–40 years, 25% were between 41–59 years, and 30% were above 60 years of age. In terms of occupation, 45% of respondents were herb sellers, 40% were nursing mothers, and 15% were traditional medical practitioners. Regarding religious, 55% were Christians, 30% were Muslims, and 15% practiced traditional religion. Educational background indicated that 40% of the respondents had no formal education, 5% had primary education, 25% had secondary education, and 30% had tertiary education.

Table 1. Demographic information of respondents.

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	09	15
Female	51	85
Age Group		
18-40 years	27	45
41-59 years	15	25
60 years above	18	30
Occupation		
Herbs Seller	27	45
Nursing Mothers	24	40
Traditional Medical Practitioner	09	15
Religion		
Christianity	33	55
Islam	18	30
Traditional	09	15
Atheist	-	-
Literacy Level		
No Formal Education	24	40
Primary	03	05
Secondary	15	25
Tertiary	18	30

3. 2. Knowledge and Use of Medicinal Plants

The findings revealed that all respondents (100%) were familiar with infantile seborrheic dermatitis. Additionally, 95% of the respondents had knowledge of herbal remedies used for its treatment. The primary source of herbal knowledge was family inheritance, with 85% learning from their parents, 10% from paid training, and 5% from books or written sources. In terms of experience, most respondents had used herbal remedies for 6–10 years (45%), followed by those with more than 11 years of experience (35%), while 20% had between 1–5 years of experience.

Figure 1. Knowledge of Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis.

Figure 2. Knowledge of Herbs Use for Treating Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis.

Figure 3. Source of Herbal Usage Knowledge.

Figure 4. Experience in the use of Herbal for Treating Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis.

3. 3. Medicinal Plants Used for Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis

The medicinal plants used for infantile seborrheic dermatitis are presented in Table 2, a total of fifteen medicinal plant species were identified as being used for the treatment of

infantile seborrheic dermatitis. These included African balsam plant, coconut plant, false cedar, healer herb, locust bean plant, mango plant, neem plant, negro pepper, onion plant, ordeal plant, pawpaw plant, ringworm plant, sandpaper plant, sausage plant, and water hyacinth.

Table 2. List of medicinal plants used in treatment of Infantile Seborrheic Dermatitis.

S/N	Common Name	Plant habit	Plants Part Used	Mode of Preparation	Solvent (Additives) used	Method of Use
1.	African balsam plant	Tree	Bark	Cook with potash/ decoction	Water	Drink for 3 day/ bath daily
2.	Coconut plant	Tree	Bark	Extraction	-	Rub on child's scalp, and then wash with shampoo.
3.	False cedar	Tree	Bark	Decoction	Water	Bathing
4.	Healer herb	Herb	Leaf	Cooking	Water	Bathing
5.	Locust bean plant	Tree	Leaf	Decoction	Water	Bathing and Drinking
6.	Mango plant	Tree	Leaf /Bark	Cooking	Water	Bathing
7.	Neem Plant	Tree	Leaf /Bark	Cooking until it turns bloodlike	Water	Bathing
8.	Negro pepper	Tree	Seed	Decoction	Water	Bathing
9.	Onion plant	Underground stem	Leaf and bark	Cook until it until it turns bloodlike	Water	Bathing
10.	Ordeal plant	Tree	bark	Decoction	Water	Bathing
11.	Pawpaw plant	Tree	Leaf	Soaking/cooking	Water	Bathing
12.	Ringworm plant	Shrub	Leaf	Cooking	Local Soap/ Water	Bathing
13.	Sand paper plant	Tree	The leaf	Squeezing	-	Rub on the affected area
14.	Sausage plant	Tree	Bark	Decoction	Water	Bathing
15.	Water hyacinth	Herb	The leaf	Cooking	Water	Bath and drink for one year above/ Bath only for less than one year old

The forms of these plants indicated that trees constituted the majority (73%), followed by herbs (13%), shrubs (7%), and underground stems (7%) (Figure 5). The most commonly used

plant parts were leaves (50%), followed by bark (39%), seeds (6%), and husks (5%) (Figure 6). The major preparation methods were cooking (47%) and decoction (35%), while soaking, extraction, and squeezing each accounted for 6% (Figure 7). Water was the most commonly used solvent (86%), whereas local soap and potash each accounted for 7% (Figure 8). Regarding the mode of administration, bathing was the most common method (72%), followed by drinking (17%) and topical rubbing (11%) (Figure 9).

Figure 5. Plant Habit.

Figure 6. Plants Part Used.

Figure 7. Mode of Preparation.

Figure 8. Solvent (Additives) used.

Figure 9. Method of Use.

4. DISCUSSION

The predominance of female respondents in this study suggests that women play a major role in traditional healthcare practices related to infant care. This observation is consistent with previous ethnobotanical studies which reported that women, particularly nursing mothers and herb sellers, often possess extensive knowledge of herbal remedies for childhood illnesses (Aworinde and Erinoso, 2015; Umoren *et al.*, 2022). Traditional medicinal knowledge is frequently transmitted through family lineage, particularly from parents or elders (Abiolu, 2018).

The high level of awareness of infantile seborrheic dermatitis among respondents indicates that the condition is commonly recognized within the community. The widespread knowledge of herbal remedies for treating this condition further highlights the reliance on traditional medicine as a primary healthcare option. In many rural and semi-urban communities, medicinal plants remain affordable and accessible alternatives to conventional medicine (Adeniran and Akindele, 2024).

The dominance of trees among the identified medicinal plants aligns with findings from other ethnobotanical surveys where trees often constitute a large proportion of medicinal species used in traditional medicine (Umoren *et al.*, 2022; Umoren *et al.*, 2025). The frequent use of leaves observed in this study is also consistent with previous reports indicating that leaves are commonly used due to their abundance and high concentration of bioactive compounds (Ajao *et al.*, 2023).

Preparation methods such as cooking and decoction were dominant among respondents because they facilitate the extraction of active phytochemicals from plant materials. Water being the most commonly used solvent reflects the simplicity and accessibility of traditional herbal preparation techniques. Bathing as the primary mode of application indicates that many of the remedies are intended for topical treatment of infant skin conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

The study highlights the significant role of traditional medicinal plants in the management of infantile seborrheic dermatitis. Indigenous knowledge of herbal medicine remains widely practiced and is largely transmitted through family lineage. The documentation of fifteen medicinal plant species reflects the rich ethnobotanical heritage of the community. However, further phytochemical, pharmacological, and toxicological studies are required to scientifically validate the efficacy and safety of these herbal remedies.

References

- [1] Abiolu, O. A. (2018). Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants in southwestern Nigeria and traditional healers' perception of indigenous knowledge digitization. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 45–56
- [2] Aboh, S. O., Ogunyemi, A. O., and Onadeko, A. A. (2023). Ethnobotanical uses of medicinal plants for dermatological diseases among the Yoruba of southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 317, 116734

- [3] Adeniran, L. A., and Akindele, O. O. (2024). Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used by indigenous people of Ilorin, North-Central Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Natural Products and Medicine*, 28(1), 34-42
- [4] Adeniyi, A., Asase, A., Ekpe, P. K., Asitoakor, B. K., Adu-Gyamfi, A. and Avekpor, P. Y. (2018). Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants from Ghana; confirmation of ethnobotanical uses, and review of biological and toxicological studies on medicinal plants used in Apra Hills Sacred Grove. *Journal of Herbal Medicine*. 14, 76-87
- [5] Ajao, A. A., Mukaila, Y. O., and Sabiu, S. (2023). Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used for the management of skin diseases in Southwestern Nigeria. *Ethnobotany Research and Applications*, 25, 1-15
- [6] Ampitan, T. A. (2013). Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants in Biu local government area of Borno state, Nigeria. *Comprehensive Journal of Herbs and Medicinal Plants*. 2(1), 7-11
- [7] Ansari, P., Reberio, A. D., Ansari, N. J., Kumar, S., Khan, J. T., Chowdhury, S., Abd El-Mordy, F. M., Hannan, J. M. A., Flatt, P. R., Abdel-Wahab, Y. H. A., and Seidel, V. (2025). Therapeutic potential of medicinal plants and their phytoconstituents in diabetes, cancer, infections, cardiovascular diseases, inflammation, and gastrointestinal disorders. *Biomedicines*, 13(2), 454
- [8] Aworinde, D. O. and Erinoso, S. M. (2015). Ethnobotanical investigation of indigenous plants used in the management of infant illnesses in Ibadan, Nigeria. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 12(5), 98-105
- [9] Hashim, A., Fatima, F., and Malave, P. (2025). Therapeutic potential of rosemary: Bridging traditional uses and modern applications. *Biotechnology Journal International*, 29(4), 1-13
- [10] Laughter, M. R., Maymone, M. B. C., and Vashi, N. A. (2021). Seborrheic dermatitis in children and adults: Epidemiology, pathophysiology, and treatment. *Dermatologic Therapy*, 34(2), e14728. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.14728>
- [11] Mangali, G. R., Evangelista, L. and Bawer, M. C. C. Ethnobotanical Survey of Selected Medical Plants Used in Children of Mabilong and Botbot Tribe in Kalinga, Philippines. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 10(3) 123-135
- [12] Nnadi, N. E., Opara, E. I., and Onyekwelu, J. C. (2021). Importance of ethnobotanical documentation in Nigerian healthcare research. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*, 21(1), 95
- [13] Odeyemi, O. O., and Amoo, S. O. (2020). Traditional medicinal plants and their therapeutic potential in Nigeria: A review. *South African Journal of Botany*, 130, 375-388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2019.12.014>
- [14] Ogun State Government (2025). Official Website for Ogun State: Who we are. Retrieved from <https://new.ogunstate.gov.ng/who-we-are.php>
- [15] Oguntibeju, O. O. (2025). The interrelationship between culture and the use of medicinal plants in healing: Perspectives from selected cultures and countries. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, 23(1), 8363-8384

- [16] Onipede, J. A., Ajayi, O. O., Umoren, O. D., Liadi, A. I. and Tijani, O. N. (2025). Physicochemical and Microbiological Assessment of Herbal-Based Therapies for Infantile Eela. *Biological and Environmental Sciences Journal for the Tropics* 22 (3): 212-220
- [17] Osifeso, O. O., Umoren, O. D., Bamidele, A. A., Obika, C. G. and Adeogun, O. A. (2025). Protective Effect of Bryophyllum pinnatum (Lam.) Oken (Miracle Leaf) Extract on Butylglycol-Induced Hepatotoxicity. *World News of Natural Sciences*. 59, 239-249
- [18] Sarsodia, G., and Dubey, R. (2025). Exploring the potential of anti-diabetic medicinal plants and phytocompounds. *Pharmacognosy Research*, 17(3), 719-727
- [19] Smith, K. P., and Tan, R. C. (2023). The challenge of pediatric seborrheic dermatitis: Emerging management perspectives. *Clinical Pediatrics Review*, 18(3), 155–164.
- [20] Umoren, O. D., Amusa, O. D. and Oladetoun, G. M. (2022). Ethno-pharmacological survey of therapeutic plants used in the treatment of paediatric diseases in two local governments in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Explorer* 2(10): 1-11
- [21] Umoren, O. D., Chukwuemeka, L. E., Adewoyin, A. A., Olaoye, O. A. Osifeso, O. O. and Nwija, M. N. (2025). Therapeutic Plants Used for Maintaining & Enhancing Health Conditions in Owode-Yewa South Local Governments, Ogun State, Nigeria: An Ethno-Pharmacological Survey. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Explorer* 5(4): 35-50
- [22] Umoren, O. D. (2021). Wild Sage (*Lantana camara*) Flower and Leave: Bactericidal Efficacy on Bacterial Growth. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Explorer* 1(4): 33-36

Pictures of the most mentioned plants used for the treatment of Infantile Eela

Plate 1. Mango plant.

Plate 2. Neem plant.

Plate 3. Pawpaw plant.